

Disaster Management Analysis in Gorontalo City

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Abstract: The research aims to determine and analyze (1) disaster management in Gorontalo City & (2) determining factors for the success of disaster management in Gorontalo City. The research approach used is a qualitative method with a descriptive research method and research procedures are carried out by observation and interviews with informants. The data analysis technique used is interactive analysis of the miles and huberman models. The results of the study indicate that (1) disaster management in Gorontalo City is focused on efforts to reduce the impact of disasters through careful planning, good coordination between various agencies, and fast and effective implementation and intense supervision/evaluation/monitoring of various management processes carried out. The main focus lies on preparedness, rapid response, and coordinated recovery after a disaster occurs. The Gorontalo City Government is trying to increase the capacity of the disaster management system, both through the formation of clear policies and training for the community and related officers. Synergy between institutions, as well as community participation are important parts in building readiness to face the threat of disasters that continue to grow. (2) the success of disaster management in Gorontalo City is greatly influenced by several important factors. The main determining factors are the quality of Human Resources (HR) who are trained and ready to face disasters, as well as adequate budget support to support disaster management activities. In addition, active community participation in mitigation activities, training, and awareness of disaster risks also play an important role in the successful implementation of disaster management policies. With these three factors, disaster management can be implemented more effectively and responsively to the various challenges that exist.

Keywords: Disaster; Mitigation; Management; Gorontalo.

INTRODUCTION

Public services at the Regional Disaster Management Agency include 3 stages, namely the pre-disaster stage, during emergency response, and post-disaster. Public services at the Regional Disaster Management Agency, especially in Gorontalo City, often experience obstacles. Based on brief interviews with each person in charge of the section in the Gorontalo City Regional Disaster Management Agency, the efforts that have been taken, especially in the pre-disaster stage by empowering the community in environmental cleaning programs by each sub-district in Gorontalo City, seem not optimal, while the emergency response and post-disaster stages experience limitations in manpower and budget if the type of disaster has a very large impact on losses.

Aware of its position as a disaster-prone country, the Indonesian government has enacted Law Number 24 of 2007 concerning Disaster Management. The law regulates the

implementation of disaster management through the National Disaster Management Agency which handles disaster management on a national scale, and the Regional Disaster Management Agency which handles disaster management in the regions. Mapping of disaster-prone areas in Hulonthalangi District, which is one of the disaster management agencies, is regulated in Law Number 24 of 2007 concerning Disaster Management. It is also regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 26 of 2015 concerning Guidelines for Coordination of Evacuation and Protection Clusters in Disaster Management and Regional Regulation of Gorontalo Province Number 3 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of Disaster Management.

Based on research by Putra & Hidayat (2013), one of the natural disasters that often occurs in Indonesia is flooding. Semarang City experiences flooding with an increasing frequency of occurrence every year. The Semarang City BPBD is guided by a number of government regulations, one of which is Semarang City Regional Regulation Number 13 of 2010 concerning the Implementation of Disaster Management. Article 18 of Semarang City Regional Regulation Number 13 of 2010 concerning the Implementation of Disaster Management divides disaster management into three stages, namely: a) Pre-disaster, b) Emergency response, and c) Post-disaster.

The effectiveness of the budget for disaster management has an average ratio of 88.11% which is in the fairly good criteria (not optimal). This shows that although most of the funds are used effectively, there is still room for improvement. So the government (BPBD Gorontalo City) needs to adopt best practices in logistics procurement and distribution, and ensure that all expenditures are on target and according to needs. Then conduct training and capacity building for disaster managers at all levels to improve the competence and efficiency of budget use. By making the above improvements, the effectiveness of the disaster management budget can be increased, so that every fund allocated can provide maximum benefits to communities affected by the disaster, and ultimately help rebuild and improve resilience (effectiveness and efficiency of disaster management) against future disasters.

Over the past 3 years, Gorontalo City has experienced many disasters, namely with an average increase of 42.16%, where the worst in 2023 was 64 non-fire disasters, which of course requires better disaster management. The results of initial observations in Gorontalo City, found 1 sub-district, namely Hulonthalangi District, where there are still many sub-districts that have not mapped disaster-prone areas, even though Hulonthalangi District is a dominant area with mountains and waters so that it will easily be affected by natural disasters. Mapping disaster-prone areas, which is one of the disaster management efforts, is also very necessary in order to provide an early warning system for the community regarding locations that are considered at high risk of disasters and locations that are safe from disasters and can provide convenience for local people to save themselves.

The results of the observation can be identified, namely, first in disaster management planning in Gorontalo City, the main problem found is the lack of mapping of disaster-prone areas, especially in Hulonthalangi District. This district has geographical characteristics in the form of mountains and waters that make it vulnerable to natural disasters such as landslides and floods. The increase in the number of non-fire disasters by 42.16% in the last three years shows the need for more mature planning. The lack of mapping hinders prevention and handling efforts, because the community does not know for sure the high-risk areas. Without proper planning, an early warning system is also difficult to develop, making the community more vulnerable to the impacts of disasters.

Both organizations in disaster management in Gorontalo City still need to be improved, especially in terms of coordination between agencies and stakeholders. In some areas, such as Hulonthalangi District, not all sub-districts have a well-organized disaster response team.

An unclear organizational structure and lack of community involvement in disaster management have led to slow responses to emergencies. In addition, human resources and infrastructure for disaster management are still limited. Atrin (2018) said that ideally, each sub-district should have a trained disaster management team and have adequate tools to deal with various possible disasters.

Third, the implementation of disaster management in Gorontalo City is often hampered by the lack of readiness of resources and equipment. In the case of non-fire disasters that continue to increase, the government's response is often slow due to the absence of standard operating procedures (SOPs) that are well implemented at the sub-district and district levels. In areas such as Hulonthalangi, which are prone to disasters, the implementation of disaster management plans is not optimal, so that the community is less educated about how to save themselves when a disaster occurs. Atrin (2018) said that effective implementation must include routine evacuation drills, provision of emergency equipment, and socialization of early warning systems in every disaster-prone sub-district.

The fourth is that monitoring and evaluation in disaster management in Gorontalo City are still less than optimal, where according to the Gorontalo City Social and Community Empowerment Service, this is because various evaluations that have been carried out have not been followed up, such as the disaster management budget which has actually decreased even though more infrastructure is needed in disaster management. The absence of a consistent evaluation mechanism to monitor the readiness of disaster-prone areas, such as in Hulonthalangi District, has resulted in some sub-districts not having carried out risk mapping. Periodic monitoring is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of the mitigation steps that have been taken and to identify weaknesses that still exist in the system. This evaluation is also important to update disaster risk maps, assess community readiness, and ensure that the early warning system is functioning properly, so that corrective actions can be taken before the next disaster occurs.

Based on the results of field interviews with the community, the Social Service and Community Empowerment and the Gorontalo City BPBD, disaster management in Gorontalo City has also been carried out in stages, namely pre-disaster, emergency response, and post-disaster where the scope of this stage is in accordance with the POAC management stages, namely planning, organizing, actuating and controlling. Pre-disaster, the Gorontalo City BPBD carries out planning and mitigation, planning how to deal with disasters and safe places to become evacuation sites when natural disasters occur, while in mitigation, socialization and training are carried out on saving oneself when a disaster occurs. Emergency Response, at this stage the BPBD immediately sends a team with complete equipment, one of which is a rubber boat to save the community and set up tents to become temporary evacuation sites. Post-Disaster, the last stage of disaster management, the BPBD team begins to clean up the disaster site and calculate the losses from damage caused by the disaster.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at the Gorontalo City Government with the main locus at the Gorontalo City BPBD. The time used to carry out this research was calculated from May 2024 to December 2024. The research approach used was a qualitative method with a descriptive research method and the research procedure was carried out by observation and interviews with informants. The data analysis technique used was interactive analysis of the miles and huberman models.

RESEARCH RESULT

1. Disaster management exposure in Gorontalo City

a. Planning

Planning in disaster management in Gorontalo City is a comprehensive, collaborative, and data-based process. This planning involves various parties, including a special drafting team, the community, academics, and non-governmental organizations. The main focus of the planning is to identify disaster risks through mapping vulnerable areas, especially for disasters that often occur such as floods in the East City, West City, and South City Districts. Contingency plans are prepared through systematic stages, starting from risk identification, emergency response scenario modeling, to simulations involving the community. This process is updated every two years to ensure data accuracy and the effectiveness of the strategies used. Evaluation of the plan is carried out through an annual coordination meeting by considering disaster incident reports, community input, and analysis from related parties.

In addition, this planning also pays special attention to vulnerable groups, such as the elderly, children, and people with disabilities. The Social Service has an important role in ensuring social protection through the provision of vulnerable group data, preparedness training, and strengthening the role of Disaster Preparedness Cadets (Tagana). Routine coordination with agencies such as BPBD, TNI, and Polri is key in preparing logistics and social assistance distribution plans. This process is designed to create synergy between various parties in disaster mitigation, while ensuring the availability of adequate resources. With this collaborative and integrated approach, Gorontalo City seeks to improve preparedness, strengthen the social protection system, and minimize the impact of disasters on the community.

b. Organizing

Organization in disaster management is carried out in a structured manner and involves various parties who coordinate with each other. The organizational structure of BPBD consists of several fields such as preparedness, logistics, rehabilitation, and emergency response, with the head of the implementation under the Regional Secretary as *ex officio*. Each field has a specific role to support the common goal, namely effective disaster management. In its operations, BPBD collaborates with related agencies such as the Social Service, PUPR, TNI, and Polri, and involves the community and the private sector. The BPBD Quick Reaction Team (TRC) consisting of dozens of personnel is the spearhead in responding to disasters, supported by logistical resources and equipment coordinated through the Operations Control Center (Pusdalops). This system ensures that every step in disaster management is integrated and based on field needs.

Cross-agency coordination is a key element in organizing, from providing logistics, preparedness training, to mobilizing resources. Each agency has complementary responsibilities, such as the Social Service which focuses on distributing aid logistics and the TNI/Polri which supports security and evacuation. BPBD also relies on an emergency command system (incident command system) to ensure that resource allocation is carried out quickly and on target. In addition, community involvement in preparedness simulations demonstrates a participatory approach that strengthens local capacity in dealing with disasters. With solid coordination and support from various parties, BPBD Gorontalo City is able to create responsive, structured, and community-oriented disaster management.

c. Implementation (Actuating)

The implementation (actuating) of disaster management in Gorontalo City has integrated efforts from various parties, including the Social Service, BPBD, and the community. The

Social Service, for example, plays an important role in evacuating affected communities, providing public kitchens, and distributing basic necessities such as basic necessities and bedding. This process is carried out through coordination with the Health Service and local volunteers to ensure that social assistance is delivered properly. On the other hand, BPBD has developed a support system, such as installing an early warning system (EWS) in disaster-prone areas, establishing evacuation routes equipped with signs, and managing emergency response posts. Through the WhatsApp group managed by Pusdalops, the community can convey disaster information quickly, so that the emergency response team can respond more effectively. This approach shows collaboration between government agencies and the community in implementing disaster management.

However, there are still several challenges faced in implementing disaster management in Gorontalo City. One of them is the delay in distributing aid in the early stages of a disaster, which often hinders the fulfillment of emergency needs such as food and clean water. In addition, the lack of clear coordination during the evacuation process, such as routes blocked by vehicles and puddles, indicates the need to improve the evacuation system. The gap in information among the community is also an obstacle, where some residents do not know the location of the evacuation that has been prepared. However, the government's attention that was seen several days after the disaster had a positive impact on recovery efforts. By overcoming these challenges, disaster management in Gorontalo City can be more responsive, organized, and centered on community needs.

d. Monitoring supervision/evaluation (Controlling)

Supervision and evaluation (controlling) in disaster management in Gorontalo City includes a series of activities involving cross-agency coordination, technology, and input from the community. The Social and Community Empowerment Service, for example, makes direct visits to affected locations to monitor the situation and receive reports from volunteers and other regional apparatuses. Evaluations are carried out through cross-agency coordination meetings organized by BPBD, where input related to aid distribution and the effectiveness of social services is analyzed to improve procedures. BPBD also relies on routine evaluations at disaster-prone points using operational vehicles and data from the community. The evaluation results are used as a basis for improving the response system.

In addition, technology-based monitoring plays an important role in this controlling process. BPBD utilizes the InaRISK application and BMKG data to conduct routine monitoring, which is updated monthly to predict potential disasters. Post-disaster evaluations involve affected communities as a significant source of feedback. Community input helps BPBD in developing better response plans, including increasing the number of evacuation routes and updating technology such as early warning systems. Although this approach is quite comprehensive, challenges such as limited access in several areas, including Hulonthalangi District, remain a major concern. Overall, monitoring and evaluation in Gorontalo City are oriented towards increasing the efficiency of disaster management through synergy between agencies, technological innovation, and community involvement.

2. Exposure to the determining factors for the success of disaster management in Gorontalo City

a. Human Resources Factors

The human resources (HR) factor in disaster management in Gorontalo City plays a very important role in ensuring readiness and effective response to disaster situations. Routine training for personnel is a top priority involving various parties, such as the Civil Service Police Unit (Pol PP), Fire Department, Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), and national institutions such as BNPB. Training includes disaster simulations, logistics

management, use of special tools, and emergency communication skills. In addition, increasing HR capacity through leadership training in emergency situations and certification is also prioritized to ensure competency according to standards. The constraint in the form of limited number of personnel is a major challenge, especially in handling large-scale disasters. This is overcome through cross-sector synergy, optimizing the role of volunteers, and utilizing communication technology.

The role of the community, especially volunteers, is a strategic component in disaster management. The Gorontalo City BPBD actively involves the community through training for disaster-resilient village volunteers (Destana), mitigation activities, and disaster simulations. Volunteers are empowered to assist in the prevention, emergency response, and rehabilitation stages, including in logistics distribution, communication, and evacuation. Volunteer management is carried out in a structured manner through basic disaster training and formal recognition to encourage active participation. Collaboration with other institutions, such as the TNI, Polri, and provincial government, is also a strategy to mobilize additional resources when faced with limitations. Overall, HR management in disaster management in Gorontalo City prioritizes collaboration, strengthening individual and community capacity, and technology-based innovation to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of disaster management.

b. Budget factors

Budget factors in disaster management in Gorontalo City are influenced by the flexibility of fund allocation and the ability to collaborate between agencies. The disaster management budget is designed based on risk analysis and priority scales set annually, but often the amount available is still limited to deal with all potential disaster scenarios. In urgent situations, emergency funds can be accessed through coordination with BPBD, which has a direct line to funding sources from the central government such as BNPB. This process is strengthened by the use of an information technology-based system to accelerate the submission of emergency needs reports. However, the main obstacle is the time for disbursement of funds which often does not match the urgency in the field. To overcome this problem, a bailout mechanism from the regular budget and temporary assistance from the private sector and donor institutions are used to ensure smooth operations in the field.

Collaboration between local governments, related agencies, and the community is a key element in managing budget constraints. In every stage of disaster management, from prevention to emergency response, collaboration with the private sector, donor agencies, and the provincial government helps fill budget gaps. In addition, budget use is directed effectively to priority needs such as logistics, security, and evacuation. A fast coordination mechanism between agencies, such as BPBD, Social Services, Pol-PP, Fire Department, ensures that budget allocations can be utilized optimally despite administrative constraints. With this approach, Gorontalo City can manage budget challenges adaptively, maximize the use of existing resources, and maintain a fast and efficient response in dealing with disaster situations.

c. Community support factors

Community support in disaster management in Gorontalo City shows a positive trend, although it still needs improvement in several aspects. Collective community awareness of disaster risks is quite good, reflected in their active participation in mitigation programs such as disaster simulations, socialization, and logistics management training at the community level. The local government, through BPBD, has made efforts to educate communities in disaster-prone areas, such as riverbanks and coastal areas, by teaching mitigation steps, evacuation, and the use of early warning systems. These efforts have succeeded in increasing the readiness of most communities, although there are certain areas that still need more attention. The relationship between the community and the

government in disaster management is quite good, with open communication and joint efforts to adjust evacuation procedures and logistics distribution to be more effective.

However, challenges still exist, especially related to equalizing community awareness and preparedness throughout Gorontalo City. Several remote areas require additional early warning devices and supporting facilities such as logistics warehouses to improve response when a disaster occurs. The government and community have collaborated to overcome this challenge, such as by submitting proposals for the procurement of additional devices to BNPB and actively involving the community in training and simulations. This growing awareness shows great potential for the people of Gorontalo City to become more resilient to disasters. However, the scope of the socialization and simulation program needs to be expanded, especially in areas with low levels of awareness. With more intensive communication and active involvement of all parties, disaster management in Gorontalo City can become more effective and inclusive.

3. Research Findings

The findings regarding the realization of disaster management funds and disaster events in Gorontalo City are presented as follows:

Figure 1: Realization of disaster management funds and disaster events in Gorontalo City

Source: Gorontalo City Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD)

Based on the graph above, it can be seen that the realization of funds for disaster management in Gorontalo City has shown a significant downward trend over the past three years. In 2021, the budget allocated was IDR 5,777,442,711, but in 2022 it decreased to IDR 5,206,560,603, and decreased further in 2023 to IDR 4,054,964,666. This decrease in funds occurred even though Gorontalo City faced a significant increase in the number of disasters. This certainly affects the capacity of the city government in responding to and handling various disaster events that occur, both in terms of direct response and post-disaster recovery efforts.

In 2021, Gorontalo City recorded 31 disasters, indicating that there were a number of incidents that required adequate handling and management. Although the available funds were sufficient to deal with these incidents, the budget reduction that occurred the following year resulted in limited resources that could be utilized. In 2022, the number of disasters increased to 35 incidents, but the allocation of disaster management funds was actually reduced, so that efforts to deal with the impact of disasters and restore post-disaster conditions became increasingly limited. This situation shows an imbalance between the number of disasters and the funds available to deal with them.

In 2023, the number of disasters in Gorontalo City increased drastically to 71 events. The increasing frequency of disasters that occur along with the decreasing budget can create tension in the capacity of the city government to provide a quick and effective response. This decrease in funds also has the potential to slow down the post-disaster rehabilitation

and reconstruction process, due to the limited funds allocated to help affected communities. This makes the situation worse, because more and more disasters occur, while existing resources are decreasing, so that disaster management can experience obstacles in meeting emergency needs.

This significant decrease in funding also risks reducing the quality and effectiveness of disaster mitigation programs carried out in Gorontalo City. Disaster mitigation programs that are ideally carried out continuously with sufficient budget allocation can help reduce the impact of disasters that occur. However, with limited funds available, the ability to implement these programs will be hampered, and the community will be increasingly vulnerable to disaster risks. Therefore, it is important for the Gorontalo City government to find solutions related to adequate funding, either through alternative fundraising, increasing budget allocations in the future, or through cooperation with related institutions to ensure effective and sustainable disaster management.

DISCUSSION

1. Disaster management in Gorontalo City

Disaster management in Gorontalo City is focused on efforts to reduce the impact of disasters through careful planning, good coordination between various agencies, and fast and effective implementation as well as intense supervision/evaluation/monitoring of various management processes carried out. The main focus lies on preparedness, rapid response, and coordinated recovery after a disaster occurs. The Gorontalo City Government is trying to increase the capacity of the disaster management system, both through the formation of clear policies and training for the community and related officers. Synergy between agencies, as well as community participation, are important parts in building readiness to face the ever-growing threat of disasters.

Disaster management in Gorontalo City focuses on well-coordinated planning, organizing, implementing, and monitoring. Planning includes risk analysis and identification of disaster priorities that must be addressed. Organizing involves collaboration between government agencies, BPBD, and the community to ensure that each party's role is running optimally. Implementation emphasizes community preparedness through simulations, logistics distribution, and effective evacuation implementation. Finally, monitoring and evaluation are carried out to assess the success of the disaster response and improve procedures based on experience and monitoring results in the field. The main focus is to create a responsive and integrated response system.

The results of each sub-focus on disaster management in Gorontalo City are described below:

a. Planning

Planning in disaster management in Gorontalo City serves as an initial step to ensure preparedness and appropriate response to disasters. The local government and related agencies design strategies based on existing disaster risk analysis, such as floods, earthquakes, and forest fires. This planning process involves mapping potential disasters in various regions using geographic data and historical statistics. Community involvement in the planning stage is essential to understand local needs and potential vulnerabilities that may affect the effectiveness of the plan. This includes the preparation of clear standard operating procedures (SOPs) for each type of disaster that may occur.

Furthermore, disaster management planning in Gorontalo City also involves the development of an emergency plan that includes evacuation routes, shelters, and aid distribution points. This plan is made by considering existing infrastructure, human resource (HR) capacity, and support from various humanitarian organizations. To maximize

the effectiveness of the planning, the city government also works with BPBD, related agencies, and local communities to identify priorities and determine the necessary budget. This aims to reduce the impact of the disaster and ensure a rapid and coordinated response.

In addition, in the planning process, the use of technology such as geographic information systems (GIS) for disaster mapping and resource planning is crucial. GIS allows authorities to visualize disaster data more accurately, which supports data-based decision-making. Increasing human resource capacity in the use of this technology is also part of the plan to strengthen disaster management planning. The implementation of this technology accelerates the process of identifying potential risks and creating strategies that are more adaptive to changing conditions, and can adapt to dynamic disaster situations.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Prasetyo et al. (2020) which states that data-based planning and risk mapping are very important in disaster management. With mature and technology-based planning, areas that are vulnerable to disasters will be better prepared to face potential threats, as well as accelerate the response to unexpected disaster events.

b. Organizing

Organization in disaster management in Gorontalo City focuses on the formation of a clear organizational structure to deal with disasters. BPBD (Regional Disaster Management Agency) acts as the main institution that coordinates all parties involved in disaster management. In addition, the City Government also forms various emergency teams consisting of government officials, TNI, Polri, volunteers, and other community organizations. This organizational structure needs to be arranged in such a way that it can provide a quick and effective response when a disaster occurs.

Effective organization also involves a clear division of tasks between the various parties involved. Each institution or agency has certain responsibilities and authorities, for example BPBD in disaster management, the Social Service in distributing social assistance, and the Health Service which is responsible for providing medical services. Coordination between agencies is very important so that every action taken supports each other and does not overlap. In addition, organization also includes the establishment of adequate and coordinated evacuation centers with a fast and accurate information system.

In addition, in organizing, community involvement is very important to support the implementation of disaster management plans. Therefore, organizing also involves the formation of community groups that are ready to be involved in disaster management, such as volunteer groups. Continuous training and socialization carried out to the community to increase their capacity in dealing with disasters is also a very important part of organizing efforts. A well-organized community can be a major force in providing emergency assistance and post-disaster recovery.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Wulandari et al. (2021) which states that organizing involving various related parties, including the community, greatly determines the success of disaster management. In this case, good coordination between agencies and active community involvement are key factors in increasing the effectiveness of disaster response.

c. Implementation (Actuating)

Implementation in disaster management in Gorontalo City involves the implementation of a plan that has been prepared by involving all previously organized parties. After planning and organizing are complete, the next step is to mobilize all parties to act according to the existing plan. Actions taken include community evacuation, assistance, and provision of medical facilities and protection in evacuation sites. Effective implementation requires high

preparedness and readiness of all parties in facing disasters.

The implementation of disaster management activities also includes the distribution of logistics and well-organized aid. The Gorontalo City Government together with BPBD and humanitarian agencies must ensure that aid distribution reaches disaster-affected communities quickly and accurately. This requires intense coordination and training for officers in the field. In addition, continuous monitoring and evaluation during the implementation of the disaster is also important to ensure that the actions taken are in accordance with the plan and there is no negligence.

Another aspect of implementation is the use of technology to support aid distribution and evacuation. The use of disaster information applications or systems that can report disaster status in real-time helps make decisions faster and more informed. The application of this technology also supports more efficient resource management and ensures that aid reaches the right point. In addition, training for volunteers is also very important to ensure that they can act effectively when a disaster occurs.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Nugroho et al. (2020) which states that effective implementation depends on high preparedness and intense coordination between agencies and the community. In this context, the use of technology and training for field officers are important factors in increasing the speed and efficiency of disaster response.

d. Monitoring supervision/evaluation (Controlling)

Monitoring and evaluation supervision is an important part of disaster management in Gorontalo City to ensure that all steps taken are in accordance with the plans and objectives set. Supervision is carried out during the disaster management process, both in terms of aid distribution, evacuation, and post-disaster recovery. This continuous monitoring ensures that the response to the disaster remains effective and efficient and reduces the potential for errors or omissions in action.

Evaluations are conducted after a disaster to assess how effective disaster management is and to identify weaknesses that need to be addressed. The results of these evaluations are used as a basis for improvement in disaster management planning and implementation in the future. Any identified weaknesses, such as slow aid distribution or lack of coordination between agencies, must be addressed immediately to improve the effectiveness of disaster management in the future.

In addition, post-disaster evaluation also includes analysis of the social, economic, and environmental impacts caused by the disaster. This is very important for determining better recovery policies and designing more effective mitigation efforts in the future. Monitoring and evaluation also provide a strong basis for updating data and increasing the capacity of human resources involved in disaster management.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Susanti et al. (2022) which states that systematic post-disaster evaluation and monitoring are very important to ensure improvements in subsequent disaster responses. This also includes increasing human resource capacity and improving information systems in disaster management.

These results are in accordance with the opinion of Widodo et al. (2021) who stated that effective disaster management requires synergistic planning, organization, and implementation between the government, community, and various related institutions, as well as continuous preparedness. This is very important to ensure a quick and appropriate response in dealing with disasters.

2. Determining factors for the success of disaster management in Gorontalo City

The success of disaster management in Gorontalo City is greatly influenced by several

important factors. The main determining factor is the quality of Human Resources (HR) who are trained and ready to face disasters, as well as adequate budget support to support disaster management activities. In addition, active community participation in mitigation activities, training, and awareness of disaster risks also play an important role in the successful implementation of disaster management policies. With these three factors, disaster management can be implemented more effectively and responsively to the various challenges that exist in disaster management in Gorontalo City.

The success of disaster management in Gorontalo City is influenced by three main factors. Well-trained Human Resources (HR) who have the ability to respond to disasters effectively are very important. Sufficient budget and timely distribution are important factors to ensure that logistics, infrastructure, and post-disaster recovery needs can be met. Community support is also key, with active participation in training and high risk awareness. These three factors support each other to create an effective disaster management system that is responsive to the challenges of disasters that continue to evolve.

The results of each sub-focus regarding the determining factors for the success of disaster management in Gorontalo City are described below:

a. Human Resources Factors

Human resources (HR) play an important role in disaster management in Gorontalo City. The success of disaster management is highly dependent on the readiness, skills, and coordination between the various parties involved. Disaster management officers, ranging from government employees, volunteers, to local communities, need to be trained continuously to be able to respond to disasters quickly and effectively. Understanding of mitigation, emergency response, and post-disaster recovery must be part of a structured training program. These skills will enable HR to be involved in providing maximum service when a disaster occurs.

On the other hand, the HR factor is also closely related to their commitment and dedication in carrying out their duties. HR management in disaster management must involve competency mapping and training needs that are in accordance with the potential for disasters in the Gorontalo City area. Training must include various technical skills, as well as the ability to work in a team in emergency conditions. Therefore, improving the quality of HR is a vital aspect that must continue to be pursued by the local government.

In addition, it is also important to provide counseling and education to the community in order to support their participation in disaster management. Human resources involved in disaster management are not only limited to government officials, but also involve the general public who are ready to help in an emergency. Therefore, counseling on disaster preparedness, initial response methods, and evacuation procedures must be expanded. Involving the community in disaster management planning and implementation will create more comprehensive preparedness at every level.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Surya et al. (2021) which states that the success of disaster management is highly dependent on the quality of the human resources involved, which requires appropriate training and strengthening of local capacity in dealing with disasters. Training and increasing the capacity of human resources are key to improving disaster response and mitigation effectively.

b. Budget factors

Adequate budget is an important factor in ensuring smooth disaster management in Gorontalo City. Without sufficient budget, disaster mitigation programs, HR training, and disaster management infrastructure development cannot be implemented optimally. Therefore, proper and efficient budget planning is needed to avoid obstacles in disaster

management. The budget must be allocated in the right proportion for various purposes, starting from preparation, response, post-disaster.

One of the challenges in managing the disaster management budget is ensuring transparency and accountability in the use of funds. Local governments must ensure that the allocated funds are used effectively and on target. Therefore, monitoring and evaluation of budget use is very important. In addition, cooperation with the private sector and international institutions can help.

In addition, budget factors also include the priority of allocating funds for the development of disaster-resilient infrastructure. For example, strengthening school buildings, hospitals, and evacuation facilities to be more resilient to potential disasters. Sustainable infrastructure development will help reduce the impact of damage when a disaster occurs. This requires careful planning and effective budget management to ensure that the budget is used to strengthen disaster resilience in Gorontalo City.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Kurniawan and Susanto (2022) who emphasized the importance of efficient and transparent budget allocation in supporting disaster preparedness and rapid response at the local level. Without an adequate budget, disaster management efforts will not be optimal.

c. Community support factors

Community involvement in disaster management is essential to create community resilience. Communities must be empowered through training and education programs on disaster preparedness. When communities have knowledge about mitigation methods and actions to take when a disaster occurs, they will be better prepared and quicker to deal with emergency situations. Therefore, efforts to build awareness and a culture of disaster response need to be prioritized at the community level.

Community empowerment also includes the formation of a reliable local volunteer network in disaster management. These volunteers will be the spearhead in responding to disasters at the grassroots level. Volunteers who have been trained and have the necessary skills will be very helpful in post-disaster rescue and recovery efforts. Thus, strengthening community participation is very necessary in optimizing disaster management in Gorontalo City.

In addition, community factors are also related to collaboration between the government and various elements of society. Communities must be involved in the planning and evaluation of disaster management programs in order to understand the steps that need to be taken and plan responses that suit their needs. Community involvement in the planning stage will increase a sense of shared responsibility in disaster management efforts.

The results of this sub-focus are in line with the statement of Yuliana et al. (2020) which states that community participation in disaster management at the local level greatly determines the effectiveness of response and recovery, as well as creating community resilience to disasters. Communities that are actively involved can reduce the impact of disasters.

The results of this focus are in line with the statement of Fauzi et al. (2020) which states that the success of disaster management is largely determined by good coordination between institutions, proper budget allocation, and active community involvement in every stage of disaster management. All of these factors are interrelated to create an effective response and reduce the impact of disasters.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that:

1. Disaster management in Gorontalo City is focused on mitigation efforts, namely reducing the impact of disasters through careful planning, good coordination between various agencies, and fast and effective implementation, as well as intense supervision / evaluation / monitoring of various management processes carried out. The main focus lies on prevention / preparedness, rapid response, and coordinated recovery after a disaster occurs. The Gorontalo City Government is trying to increase the capacity of the disaster management system, both through the formation of clear policies, and training for the community and related officers. Synergy between institutions, as well as community participation are important parts in building preparedness to face the threat of disasters that continue to grow every year.
2. The success of disaster management in Gorontalo City is greatly influenced by several important factors. The main determining factors are the quality of Human Resources (HR) who are trained and ready to face disasters, the quantity of supporting facilities and infrastructure for disaster management, and adequate budget support to support disaster management efforts in Gorontalo City. In addition, active community participation in mitigation activities, training, and awareness of disaster mitigation and risk also play an important role in the successful implementation of disaster management policies. With these three factors, disaster management can be implemented more effectively and responsively to the various challenges that exist.

SUGGESTION

Based on the research results and conclusions outlined above, the suggestions for this research are as follows:

1. The Gorontalo City Government should increase the budget allocation for disaster management, considering the decrease in funds that could potentially affect disaster preparedness and response. In addition, coordination between government agencies and the community needs to be strengthened to ensure that the early warning system and evacuation procedures run more effectively. The addition of regular disaster training and simulations will strengthen community resilience in facing various disaster threats.
2. Improving the quality of existing human resources and the capacity of supporting infrastructure in the Gorontalo City BPBD environment. In order to support disaster management efforts, both in the pre-disaster, disaster, and post-disaster phases in Gorontalo City.
3. The Gorontalo City BPBD needs to expand the reach of socialization and disaster simulations in areas that still receive less attention, especially in remote areas. In addition, support for the procurement of disaster management equipment, such as additional early warning devices (EWS) in disaster-prone areas, must be immediately sought by submitting further proposals to the central and provincial governments. Intensive communication with the community is also important to increase awareness and active involvement in disaster management.
4. The Gorontalo City Social and Community Empowerment Service must focus on strengthening community participation in disaster management, especially in terms of mitigation education and preparedness training. Community empowerment and volunteer programs need to be expanded to involve more local elements in disaster mitigation and response activities. The Social Service also needs to strengthen existing social networks to accelerate the response in distributing aid when a disaster occurs.
5. Satpol-PP and Fire Department of Gorontalo City should increase supervision of the fulfillment of security of infrastructure and safety standards in disaster-prone areas, especially fires. Including ensuring that public facilities have adequate disaster

mitigation systems. In addition, Satpol-PP and Fire Department can play a role in implementing natural disaster and fire evacuation simulations by involving the community to improve discipline and direct involvement in disaster preparedness.

6. The Gorontalo City Health Office needs to improve the preparedness of health facilities in facing disasters by adding training related to first aid, medical evacuation, and handling disaster victims. In addition, the Health Office also needs to strengthen the health information system to facilitate coordination in providing post-disaster medical services, as well as increasing regular health checks in disaster-prone areas.
7. Bassarnas Gorontalo should increase the capacity of the rescue team by increasing routine training, and strengthening coordination with related agencies, such as BPBD, Fire Department, and related OPDs. Rescue and evacuation equipment also needs to be updated and added according to the needs of disaster-prone areas, especially in coastal areas and hard-to-reach areas.
8. The TNI and Polri in Gorontalo City need to be more active in carrying out evacuation and security operations during disasters, as well as strengthening their role in disaster training and simulations. They are also expected to play a greater role in socializing emergency procedures and increasing logistical capacity to support effective disaster management.
9. Community leaders in Gorontalo City need to be more active in raising public awareness of the importance of disaster mitigation. They can act as agents of change by disseminating information and encouraging community participation in disaster training and simulation activities. The community should also increase awareness of disaster risks and engage in various activities that support disaster preparedness and rapid response.
10. NGOs and Disaster Volunteers in Gorontalo City should strengthen collaboration with the government and community in supporting more inclusive disaster management programs. They can play a role in expanding access to information, about disaster mitigation and can facilitate training and resources for the community, especially in areas that are vulnerable to disasters. Post-disaster assistance is also important to help the community in the recovery process.

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